

THE FINANCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF ECO-FRIENDLY PRODUCTS
ON A LOCAL ICE CREAM SHOP

The Financial and Environmental Impacts of Eco-Friendly Products on Small Businesses

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Introduction

Despite the fact that scientists have broken down styrofoam and studied it for the past 20 years, there are still many unknowns about this material. Styrofoam is a material that is most often used as packaging in the food service industry. The reason styrofoam is so popular is that it keeps the hot foods hot, while simultaneously keeping cold foods cold. The downfall to this material is that it is not biodegradable, it cannot be decomposed by organisms and bacteria. While many businesses have switched from styrofoam to more environmentally friendly products, others have stuck with the lightweight bowls because they are cheaper and larger in quantity, a golden pairing for a small business (Chandra, Kohn, Pawlitz, & Powell, 2016).

Styrofoam, the white unrecyclable containers that you have probably drank soda from or ate leftover funnel cake out of at one point or another is actually not styrofoam.

STYROFOAM™ is a material that was invented in 1941 by Dow Chemical: Its main purpose is building insulation and has been never been used to hold food or beverages. Tim Lacey, business director for building solutions in the Americas at Dow has stated that the STYROFOAM™ that is produced by their company is strictly for the purpose of building insulation and he is confused as to why people keep misusing its name to label other things (DePillis). This leaves the obvious question then of what are these “styrofoam” containers called and how are they made?

After looking at all of the research done in the last 30 years, I noticed a trend: With all of the recent news regarding big businesses taking action in favor of eco-friendly products, I wondered what other businesses were doing. There did not seem to be articles about local businesses and if they had been doing anything similar to McDonald’s, Starbucks, or Dunkin’

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Donuts. This interested me and I decided that I would start looking for certain gaps in this topic to further study myself. These studies narrowed my search topic from plastic products in general to polystyrene products specifically. No studies had been done within my local community, so I chose my local ice cream shop to study further.

What is Polystyrene?

Polystyrene is the main chemical used in creating “styrofoam” containers. Polystyrene is the connection of multiple styrene molecules; when they are bonded together, chains of polystyrene are created. The chemical formula of one styrene molecule is $(C_8H_8)_n$. It is made up of carbon and hydrogen atoms that are connected in a long chain with alternating carbon centers. These chains are then attached to phenyl groups, benzene rings that are connected to a chain of six or more carbons. When these two groups attach, they create styrene molecules; when those attach, polystyrene molecules are created. Food containers and cups are made from millions of these pre-expanded polystyrene beads (EPS). The expansion of these beads accounts for the lightweight and low density that foam containers have.

Health Dangers

Martin B. Hocking, an associate professor of chemistry at the University of Victoria in British Columbia did a quantitative analysis about the ongoing debate of paper versus polystyrene containers used in the fast food business. Hocking concluded at the end of his study that polystyrene cups should be treated the same as paper cups when it comes to environmental impact. This 1991 study was disproved in a paper published later that year. Henry A. Wells is a professor in the Department of Forest Products at the University of Minnesota and has studied Environmental Science for the past 30 years. In his article, Wells argues Hocking’s main

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argument was “based off a computational error and exaggerates the environmental impact of paper production by citing outdated effluent data and omits discussion of some important factors that should be weighed in the decision” (Wells, 1991). In the same compilation of articles, Neil McCubbin writes about another error found within Hocking’s report. He claims that Hocking used a previous article of his to reference in the paper however, the information that Hocking used was wrong. The chemistry professor used an article written 8 years prior called the “Air and Water Pollution Control training manual” (Wells, 1991). Wells states that he has written many public and more recent articles and manuals regarding the same situation that has more reliable evidence that should have been used in the report. Bonnie Camo, an expert in the field of When all of the correct and most up-to-date data is being used, it is clear to see that paper products have less of a detrimental impact on the environment than the polystyrene products (Camo, 1991).

While Hocking, Wells, McCubbin, and Camo all wrote about the environmental impacts of both paper and polystyrene cups, there are many dangers when it is used for food packaging and serving. Maryland, specifically Sen. Cheryl Kagan and Del. Brooke Lierman, is introducing a ban on all polystyrene products in the fast food business. This ban comes from the discovery of cancer-causing chemicals weaved in the expanded polystyrene beads that make up these food containers (Bruno, 2017). This discovery was further confirmed by the Agency for Research on Cancer and the National Toxicology in a study they conducted in the spring of 2017.

National Level Regulations

Many local legislatures are in debate about the topic of polystyrene and whether or not it should be banned from use due to its environmental and health detriments. Cities like New York City, Seattle, Portland, Miami Beach and many more have already passed laws banning the use

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of styrofoam in the food packaging industry (MacEachern, 2016). In fact Mayor de Blasio of New York City has announced that single-use (unable to be recycled or reused) polystyrene containers would be banned come January 2019 (“Mayor Announces Ban”, 2018). These cities are leading the way for many others, both locally and on the state level to consider the banning of polystyrene containers in at least the food packaging industry. Maryland state senator and delegate, Cheryl Kagan and Brooke Lierman respectively have introduced a state-wide ban that will be debated in the state house. It will determine whether or not polystyrene should be allowed in the food packaging and supplying industry (Bruno, 2016). Hawaii is also doing something similar as they are taking some progressive steps toward becoming the first state to introduce a state-wide polystyrene ban in the country. It is no surprise that a state like Hawaii would be quick in accepting a plan that bans polystyrene because of its small and many islands. It is much easier on these islands for ESP containers and other debris to get blown into the oceans and harm the marine life than it is in a state like Pennsylvania (Cirino, 2018).

Other than state and local governments taking action against these polystyrene containers, nationally well known businesses are also doing their part to help the issue. Three major corporations have publicly expressed their actions against the use of foam containers: McDonald’s, Starbucks, and Dunkin’ Donuts. McDonald’s announced on its website that it would begin to phase out its polystyrene cups by the end of the year. This action is not a surprising one to many considering McDonald’s did get rid of their clamshell containers just over 25 years ago; the only surprising part is the amount of time it took between getting rid of the clamshells and finally phasing out the foam cups (Reed, 2018). Starbucks, the most popular coffee place in America, has also publicly announced they will be getting rid of their foam cups.

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In return for a better alternative to the now used foam cups, Starbucks will award the winner \$10 million dollars (Smith, 2018). Following in the footsteps of both other companies, Dunkin' Donuts, another one of the most popular places to get coffee announced they will be taking similar progressive actions to reduce their environmental impacts. They are implementing the same policies as their international stores that have already banned the use of foam cups and now use a safer paper alternative; the company announced there will be no more polystyrene foam cups produced or used by 2020 (Pisani, 2018).

Local Business Attention

After seeing headline after headline of big corporations getting rid of polystyrene cups and containers, local businesses are starting to take notice. Here in Berks County specifically, two business owners saw the actions of the three large businesses and decided they wanted to help. They found an eco-friendly way of replacing plastic straws using a biodegradable paper material that they also believe can be used to replace other ESP containers (Pena, 2018).

Many of the businesses in my local area use polystyrene containers in their food packaging and "to-go" boxes. For example, local my ice cream shop uses polystyrene containers from Dart packaging; they come in six different sizes and are used for ice cream scoops, sundaes, milkshakes, and floats. They have not yet switched over to a more eco-friendly option to replace their polystyrene bowls; however, they are not the only small business faced with this challenge. Other local shops include a donut store, pizza place, and café, all places that are working on finding a more eco-friendly solution to their polystyrene containers. Big businesses like McDonald's, Starbucks, and Dunkin' Donuts bring in revenue everyday; they can afford to switch to a more eco-friendly product even if it may cost a few cents more per package. Small

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businesses that are strictly local (with maybe one or two locations only) have to think about budgeting more when it comes to small things like changing from cheap polystyrene bowls to more expensive biodegradable ones for example. Then comes the question of whether or not the environmental impacts will outweigh the financial ones, which this paper will seek the answer. I narrowed it down to the research question of “Can small businesses change their products to become more eco-friendly without breaking the bank?”

Rationale for Chosen Method

Although there has been past research conducted on the effects of polystyrene in the environment, nothing has been done with regards to small business food packaging to my knowledge. With that in mind, I had to think of how I could test these effects in the context of my own research. I decided to take a triangular approach so that I would be able to link all of my results together in a sound suggestion to the boss of the local ice cream shop.

I will be conducting a mixed method by integrating both qualitative and quantitative studies. My first study will be an observational study: I will sit in my local ice cream shop on two nights in December and record the number of polystyrene bowls that are handed out in a two hour window. My second study is a cost benefit analysis to determine the allocated budget for food containers at this ice cream shop. My third study is a group of three scientific experiments that serve the purpose of both discovering the negative effects of polystyrene and testing three different types of bowls to find the best one to use in food packaging.

These studies are most effective for my tests because not only do I have to conclude that polystyrene is dangerous, I have to suggest an alternate material that could take its spot: one that is better for both the environment and the budget. Without the observational study, I would not

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have a base number of bowls given out on any night at the ice cream shop that I would use in my cost benefit analysis. This would help the second part of my plan: suggesting an alternative material that is better for the budget. The set of three experiments tackles the first part, “better for the environment” by mimicking real life situations and observing the effects that occur between the three different materials of bowls: polystyrene, natural plant fiber, and paper.

Methodology

Procedures

Observational Study

For my observational study, I will sitting in my local ice cream shop and tallying the number of each sized bowl are handed out on a given Friday night. I will mark in my chart each time a bowl is given out and after the shift ends, I will total the numbers up and average out the totals. This type of observational study is appropriate because it will give me quantitative data that in the most accurate way possible in order to better understand how many bowls the company goes through each night on average.

However, there are variables to consider with this type of study. Since my local ice cream shop is an ice cream shop, the winter months when these observations will be happening are not the prime business times for selling ice cream. Friday nights do get busy but they do not compare to the popularity of a Friday night in the middle of July. I will take this into account but the four hours spent observing and tallying bowls should give me an accurate number to use as my foundation.

Scientific Experiments

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The next study I will be conducting will be an experiment on the three different types of bowls. This will contain a series of small tests in order to find out which type of bowl would do its job most efficiently. The small tests will include burning the bowls, dissolving them in acetone, and watching their ability to hold hot and cold foods constant for long periods of time. I will be doing three trials for each of three tests and then average out the answers in order to get the most accurate result. To burn the bowls, I will place one in a ventilation hood and set it on fire; then I will observe and record the time it took for it to fully burn. Then I will see if there is a way to test for what was given off during the burning and if that is possible, I will also be recording that information. This would show the environmental impact of burning these bowls as a way of disposing of them. Dissolving the bowls in water will be tested by placing a section of the bowl into a container of water and then watching how long it takes for it to completely dissolve if it even does. That time will be recorded and this test would show the impact it would have on the marine life and ecosystem that accompanies it. The third and final test would be a timing of how long it takes a small scoop of ice cream to melt in each of the three bowls. The reason that many businesses choose to use polystyrene bowls is because of the fact that it does such an effective job of keeping hot foods hot and cold foods cold for long periods of time.

Cost Benefit Analysis

Lastly, I will be conducting a cost benefit analysis of each of the three types of bowls; through this I hope to find that the two alternative bowl materials will be cheaper or just barely more expensive than the polystyrene ones. If the price is a bit higher, I hope to show through my experiment that the environmental impacts outweigh the low price. To complete my cost benefit analysis, I will be recording the prices per unit of 4 different sizes of polystyrene bowls that my

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local ice cream shop give out for various products. I will then find that product online and record the cost per boxes of each product. For the polystyrene and paper products, I will be using the Restaurant Store online store because that is the actual place the my local ice cream shop receives their bowls. Green Paper Products will be the source for the natural plant fiber bowl orders.

Measures

Observational Study

For my observational study, I will be using the chart provided in the Appendix to tally the number of polystyrene bowls handed out for the two-hour shift. I will also be tallying the total number of bowls that are handed out on the night in order to get a percentage of how many bowls are actually given out specific to that night.

Experiments testing solubility, insulation ability, and burning

For my experiment, I will be recording the results of all three tests in different data tables. The data tables can be found in the Appendix along with the results filled in.

Cost Benefit Analysis

I used a spreadsheet in Google Sheets in order to formulate all of my data. The Restaurant Store online ordering system has a set price for one to two cases and another slightly lower price for three to nine cases. I used those prices and multiplied them by number of cases in order to get a set price for any number of cases ordered. I used this same process for my natural plant fiber bowls from Green Paper Products, and my paper bowls from the Restaurant Store.

Discussion

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Through my multiple experiments, both qualitative and quantitative, I have come to the conclusion that polystyrene is extremely harmful to the environment. Mixed with the past data from experiments done on this topic and the data that I found from my own tests, polystyrene is too dangerous to be using in food packaging containers.

Results

I found that on December 7, 2018 between 6-8 pm, 17 out of the 31 total dishes handed out were polystyrene, coming to about 53.3%. On December 14, 2018 in the same time frame, 17 out of the 57 total dishes were polystyrene, about 44.4%. This led me to conclude almost half of the bowls on a given night are polystyrene, and even higher percent in the summer. I saw from this that my local ice cream shop was going through case after case and in the summer it would cost more per case: money that the business just doesn't have to spare. This would be my baseline for finding the right alternative material in my cost benefit analysis. The limitations to this were ice cream stores, are busiest in the summer and Friday nights are the most popular nights. My experiment was done in the middle of winter, so I did not expect for the most accurate numbers to be seen. To my surprise however, there was a line out the door for about a half hour, which is more than I thought I would get. The data numbers are definitely under what they would project had this experiment been done on two weekends in June, but the numbers were still significant for me to make a conclusion.

I noticed there was a clear decrease in the time it took for the polystyrene bowls to burn compared to the time it took for the other two - paper and natural plant fiber - to burn. For all three trials in the polystyrene bowls, it was less than 5.5 seconds on average for it to completely be burned. It was about 32 seconds for the plant fiber bowls and about 45 seconds for the paper

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bowls. There was a sharp drop in the time that it took for the polystyrene bowls to completely dissolve in the acetone compared to the time it took for the paper and the plant fibers ones. The polystyrene bowls averaged 4.6 seconds for the entire bowl to dissolve; however, both the plant fiber and the paper bowls took over a minute to even show signs of deformities. If the bowl took over a minute, I wrote in “Never Deformed”; I ended up doing this for both of the other two materials. There were no visible changes from the moment I submerged the bowl in the acetone to the moment it hit the minute mark and I removed it. The polystyrene immediately dissolved upon making contact with the acetone and in a matter of seconds the bowl was nothing more than a pile of ‘goo’. The limitations to this experiment were that without the ability to be in an actual lab with the proper materials and tools needed to accurately measure the chemicals released into the air, I was not able to have the most precise measurements. This experiment would also be unethical unless tested in a controlled laboratory, which I was unable to do. I can not burn the polystyrene because the chemicals that get released into the air are highly toxic to humans. I could not test the dissolving in water because it would take much longer than an optimal experiment so we used acetone which are both polar substances so they would produce the same effects however the acetone was much faster.

I saw in my cost benefit analysis that the polystyrene bowls were cheaper than both of the other materials, paper and plant fiber. It also showed that the natural plant fiber bowls were too expensive per case of 1000 when it came to the ordering costs, which changed the decision from 3 bowls down to 2: paper or polystyrene. My analysis was limited because I only compared two alternatives to the current material bowl that is used now. Given more time, materials, and a wider research scope, I would have research more alternatives.

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After I completed my three methods of data collection, I began to analyze how the connected to each other. I wanted to triangulate the results to centralize all of my data into one concise conclusion. After I completed the experiment, both the paper and the polystyrene bowls were equal in benefits and detriments. Through the results of my cost benefit analysis though, I was able to rule out the option of the natural plant fiber bowls.. Because the price of the paper bowls was much cheaper, it was becoming the more obvious choice.

From watching and recording the number of polystyrene bowls given out on two given nights, I was able to see how to polystyrene bowls held in the ice cream. The way these bowls are designed is to cheaply keep heat and cold in to restrict cooling and melting respectively. I saw that the polystyrene bowls were able to keep the ice cream cold for a long period of time, not allowing anything to melt while the customer was enjoying it. This made me wonder if any of the other bowls could do that same job which led me to think about my experiments.

My observational study gave me a foundation for the number of bowls that are used on a given night which I could then use to calculate the number of bowls over about a month are used. This number would then be my starter for figuring how much much money would be spent on bowls per month in my cost benefit analysis. This would easily allow me to compare the alternatives and see if they are more cost effective.

Implications & Recommendations

After my interview with the boss of my local ice cream shop and my experiments, I have concluded that the best alternative for the current polystyrene bowls are paper bowls. The paper bowls proved the clear winner in both the solubility and melting tests. Although the cost per case is higher than the cases of polystyrene cases, both the owner and her husband have expressed

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interest in switching away from polystyrene bowls. They have thought about adding their logo onto the bowls in order to present a more professional look to the customers.

After conducting all the studies, I would recommend a switch from polystyrene bowls to paper bowls. The price of the bowls is a decent amount higher, approximately \$83 per case, however the environmental impacts would greatly outweigh the financial ones. The switch would ideally be made in the summertime when just about a hundred bowls sell each night and thousands of dollars are brought in for the business. This would lessen the blow on the budget since my local ice cream shop is a small business with only one location and a tight budget already. Switching in the summer would also create a smoother transition in regards to the cost because more money made in the summer can be set aside to purchasing paper bowls in the winter seasons when sales aren't as high.

I am hoping that if my local ice cream shop can make this transition, it would set a precedent for the other small businesses near it. Not only will my local ice cream shop gain popularity within its community, but hopefully it will influence other places to make changes similar to the one they did.

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